

A Study on Assessment of Cognitive Function in Patient of Unipolar Depression in a Tertiary Care Centre

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Abstract:

Aim: The aim of present study was to assessment of cognitive function in unipolar depression patient tertiary care.

Methods: The study was carried out in Integral Institute of Medical Science and Research, Lucknow, UP, India. The study included 100 consecutive patients who were visited in both IPD & OPD during 18 months w.e.f. 01st October 2022 to 30st April 2024.

Results: In comparison, the control group consisted of 52.00% males and 48.00% females. Statistical analysis using a chi-square test demonstrated no significant difference in gender distribution between the two groups. Among the patients, 50.00% had medical comorbidities, compared to 30% (15 individuals) in the control group. Specifically, diabetes is reported in 28% (14 individuals) of the case group versus 18% (9 individuals) in the control group, hypertension in 14% (7 individuals) versus 8% (4 individuals), and hypothyroidism in 8% (4 individuals) versus 4% (2 individuals). Furthermore, 40.00% of the patients had experienced previous depressive episodes according to ICD-10 criteria. A notable finding is that 10.00% of the patients exhibited atypical presentation. Among the patients, 50.00% exhibited mild depression, with a mean score of 16.84 and a standard deviation of 2.11. Additionally, 26.00% of the patients had moderate depression, characterized by a mean score of 25.48 and a standard deviation of 2.15. Notably, 24.00% of the patients demonstrated severe depression, with a considerably higher mean score of 54.84 and a standard deviation of 4.57.

Conclusion: The study highlights the significant burden of depressive symptoms experienced by individuals with unipolar depression and underscores the intricate relationship between cognitive impairments and depressive symptomatology. Tailored interventions addressing both cognitive functioning and depressive symptoms are crucial for optimizing outcomes and improving the well-being of patients. Early detection, comprehensive assessment, and personalized management strategies are essential in psychiatric settings to enhance patient care.

Keywords: Cognitive Function, Unipolar Depression.

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Introduction

Cognition, in a broad context, refers to the processing of information and encompasses various high-level mental functions. These functions include thinking, memory, perception, motivation, skilled movements, and language. Within the brain,

the hippocampus plays a crucial role in the neural circuitry associated with cognitive functions such as learning and memory. Cognition pertains to the perceptual and intellectual aspects of mental functioning. Assessing the integrity or adequacy of

cognition involves evaluating specific functions, including orientation, the capacity to acquire essential skills, problem-solving ability, abstract thinking, reasoning, judgment-making, event retention and recall, mathematical proficiency, symbol manipulation, control over basic reactions and behavior, language use and comprehension, attention, perception, and praxis. [1] Cognitive impairments can lead to a lack of ability to: Pay Attention, Remember and Recall information, Initiate speech, Respond to information quickly, Process information quickly, Think critically, plan, organize and solve problems.

The subsequent inquiries must be explored concerning psychiatric disorders and cognitive decline. [2] Cognitive function is supported by neural circuits comprising numerous neurotransmitter systems and interconnecting regions of the basal ganglia, thalamus, and cortex in healthy adults. [3] As an illustration, circuits that connect the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and the dorsolateral caudate nucleus are implicated in the processes of programming and planning. Conversely, circuits that link the anterior cingulate cortex to the nucleus accumbens are crucial for the act of making decisions. Circuits connecting the ventromedial caudate to the orbito-prefrontal cortex are linked to response inhibition. Cognitive deficit are common in late onset depression particularly in the area of episodic memory. Measured depressive disorder can cause cognitive impairment which includes memory loss, learning difficulties and reduced executive functioning. Cognitive impairment in acute phase of illness has been frequently reported.

The hippocampus is pivotal for declarative learning and memory, serving as a hub connected to various cortical regions, and holds particular significance in the integration of cognitive and emotional processes. [4,5] Several neural circuits implicated in cognitive functions exhibit some overlap with those influencing mood and emotion. These circuits are subject to reciprocal connectivity with the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and amygdala, both integral to emotional processes.⁵ The cohesive functioning of these circuits may exert a substantial impact on the interplay between cognition and mood disorders. [6]

Several assessment tools are accessible for the evaluation of specific cognitive functions. However, the assortment of tools employed in clinical trials has complicated the advancement of understanding cognitive symptoms in depression, introducing variability in outcomes. It is imperative to establish a consensus cognitive battery for Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) clinical trials, modeled after the tool developed by the Measurement And Treatment to Improve Cognition in Schizophrenia (MATRICS) group for

schizophrenia trials. [7] Unipolar depression is widespread and has significant disabling effects. According to community surveys conducted in 14 countries, the lifetime prevalence of unipolar depressive disorders is approximately 12 percent. [8,9]

The aim of present study was to assessment of cognitive function in unipolar depression patient tertiary care.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out in Integral Institute of Medical science and research, Lucknow, UP, India. The study included 100 patients (50 per group) during the period of 18 months w.e.f. 01st October 2022 to 30st April 2024.

Inclusion Criteria for Cases

- All patients of unipolar depression (diagnosed as per ICD 10) between ages 18 to 50 years, drug naïve and giving informed consent to participate in the study
- All patients of recurrent depressive disorder in relapse (diagnosed as per ICD 10) and not on any psychotropic drugs for at least 01 month before presentation.

Exclusion Criteria for Cases

- Patients not giving informed consent
- Patients already on drugs/taken psychotropic within 01 month before evaluation
- Patients with known coexisting co morbidities like dementia, substance abuse disorders, mental retardation, bipolar disorder, psychotic symptoms which impair cognition independently
- Patients with history of any significant head injury and or epilepsy

Inclusion Criteria for Control

- Healthy relatives of patients/ independent participants, volunteers, matching with socio demographic details same as of case group, with a MMSE score >28 set as a prognostic for the selection of control

Exclusion Criteria for Control

- Participants <18 years age and >50 years age
- Participants not giving informed consent
- Participants were assessed individually in a quiet and comfortable environment within the psychiatric outpatient department.
- Case of unipolar depression freshly diagnosed as per criteria of ICD 10 and diagnosed cases of unipolar depressive episode, recurrent depressive disorder that have discontinued medicine for more than a month and become symptomatic.

- Subsequently, participants underwent cognitive assessment using the PGI BBD memory scale in which following domains are seen-remote memory, recent memory, mental balance, attention and concentration, delayed recall, immediate recall, retention for similar pairs, retention for dissimilar pairs, visual retention, recognition.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software (SPSS Inc.,

Chicago, IL, USA) for the Windows program (26.0 version). The continuous variables were evaluated by mean (standard deviation) or range value when required. The dichotomous variables were presented in number/frequency and were analyzed using Chi-square. To compare the means between the two or more groups, analysis by Student t-test was used.

Results

Table 1: Comparison of Demographic Characteristics between Patients with Unipolar Depression (CASE) and Healthy Controls (CONTROL)

Characteristic	Case (N=50)		Control (N=50)		P-Value
	Mean/N	SD/%	Mean/N	SD/%	
Age (years)	41.5	8.3	40.8	6.7	t=0.4640 p=0.6437
18-30	4	8.00%	3	6.00%	X=0.2577 p=0.8791
31-40	20	40.00%	22	44.00%	
41-50	26	52.00%	25	50.00%	
Gender					
Male	28	56.00%	26	52.00%	X=0.1610 p=0.6882
Female	22	44.00%	24	48.00%	

In terms of age, the mean age of the patients with unipolar depression was 41.5 years, with a standard deviation of 8.3, while the control group exhibited a mean age of 40.8 years, with a standard deviation of 6.7. A t-test revealed no significant difference in age distribution between the two groups (t=0.4640, p=0.6437), indicating that age did not play a significant role in the observed differences. Additionally, the distribution of age ranges (18-30, 31-40, and 41-50 years) did not exhibit any

significant discrepancy between the two groups (X=0.2577, p=0.8791), indicating a balanced distribution across different age categories. Furthermore, the gender composition revealed that 56.00% of patients with unipolar depression were male, while 44.00% were female. In comparison, the control group consisted of 52.00% males and 48.00% females. Statistical analysis using a chi-square test demonstrated no significant difference in gender distribution between the two groups.

Table 2: Description of Clinical Characteristics of Patients with Unipolar Depression

	Case (N=50)		Control (N=50)		
	N	%	N	%	
Medical Comorbidity	25	50.00%	15	30.00%	
Medical Comorbidity	Diabetes	14	28.00%	9	18.00%
	Hypertension	7	14.00%	4	8.00%
	Hypothyroidism	4	8.00%	2	4.00%
Number of patients having Previous depressive Episodes according to ICD-10	20	40.00%	-	-	
Atypical Presentation	5	10.00%	-	-	

Among the patients, 50.00% had medical comorbidities, compared to 30% (15 individuals) in the control group. Specifically, diabetes is reported in 28% (14 individuals) of the case group versus 18% (9 individuals) in the control group, hypertension in 14% (7 individuals) versus 8% (4

individuals), and hypothyroidism in 8% (4 individuals) versus 4% (2 individuals). Furthermore, 40.00% of the patients had experienced previous depressive episodes according to ICD-10 criteria. A notable finding is that 10.00% of the patients exhibited atypical presentation.

Table 3: Severity of depression According to BDI scale in Patients with Unipolar Depression

Severity of depression	Case (n=50)		
	N	%	Score
Mild (14-19)	25	50.00%	16.84±2.11
Moderate (20-28)	13	26.00%	25.48±2.15
Severe (29-63)	12	24.00%	54.84±4.57

Among the patients, 50.00% exhibited mild depression, with a mean score of 16.84 and a standard deviation of 2.11. Additionally, 26.00% of the patients had moderate depression, characterized by a mean score of 25.48 and a standard deviation of 2.15. Notably, 24.00% of the patients demonstrated severe depression, with a considerably higher mean score of 54.84 and a standard deviation of 4.57.

Discussion

Depression is a disorder of major public health importance, in terms of its prevalence and the suffering, dysfunction, morbidity, and economic burden. Depression is more common in women than men. The report on Global Burden of Disease estimates the point prevalence of unipolar depressive episodes to be 1.9% for men and 3.2% for women, and the one-year prevalence has been estimated to be 5.8% for men and 9.5% for women. It is estimated that by the year 2020 if current trends for demographic and epidemiological transition continue, the burden of depression will increase to 5.7% of the total burden of disease and it would be the second leading cause of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs), second only to ischemic heart disease. [10]

Our findings were that the Age distribution showed no significant difference between groups ($p=0.6437$), with both exhibiting balanced representation across age categories ($p=0.8791$). Similarly, gender distribution didn't vary significantly ($p=0.6882$), with 56.00% of patients being male and 44.00% female, while the control group comprised 52.00% males and 48.00% females. Additionally, marital status ($p=0.5644$) and education level ($p=0.7248$) were comparable between the two cohorts. The exploration of cognitive symptoms in major depressive disorder (MDD) patients sheds light on an often-overlooked aspect of the condition, indicating its multifaceted nature beyond mood disturbances. Despite the recognition of cognitive impairments in MDD, the precise prevalence of these symptoms remains elusive, as highlighted by various studies. [11-14] This uncertainty underscores the complexity of assessing cognitive functions in individuals with depression and emphasizes the need for further research in this area.

The study underscores the substantial burden of medical comorbidities, notably diabetes, hypertension, and hypothyroidism, among unipolar depression patients. Recurrence of depressive episodes and atypical presentations further complicate clinical management. This emphasizes the necessity of comprehensive assessments and personalized interventions addressing both psychiatric and medical components of depression. 40 % of patient in our study had previous

depressive Episodes. Dold, M et al., 2016 [15] showed that 89.8% of the whole study sample suffered from a recurrent depressive disorder. They also found that about one third of the participants were inpatients and 49% exhibited at least one somatic comorbidity with hypertension as the leading secondary diagnosis (19.4%) followed by thyroid diseases (16.5%). With regard to psychiatric comorbidities, a concomitant anxiety disorder was present in 22.1% of the enrolled depressive patients. Our findings were partly in line with previous studies. According to the literature, depression with atypical features was more common in bipolar II than in unipolar depressed patients. [16]

In our study the Severity of depression in Patients with Unipolar Depression showed that half of the patient had mild depression. In contrast, Kishore K et al., 2024 [17] found that the majority of the cases, that is, 65%, were suffering from moderate depression. Mild depression was found in 20% cases. 15% were suffering from severe depression. It is generally known that major depression episodes can cause cognitive impairment. Deficits in alertness, psychomotor speed, sustained attention, memory, and executive functioning during a major depressive episode have been documented in a number of meta-analyses. [18-20]

This study on cognitive functions in patients with unipolar depression opens up several avenues for future research and clinical practice. Firstly, further longitudinal studies are warranted to better understand the trajectory of cognitive impairments in depression, including their persistence and potential for improvement with treatment interventions. Additionally, investigating the underlying neurobiological mechanisms contributing to cognitive dysfunction in depression could provide valuable insights into novel therapeutic targets. Furthermore, given the diverse presentation of cognitive deficits in depression, personalized assessment tools and interventions tailored to individual patient profiles should be developed and validated. Integration of cognitive assessment into routine clinical practice guidelines for depression management is recommended, alongside increased awareness among healthcare professionals regarding the significance of cognitive symptoms in treatment planning. Finally, addressing the complex interplay between psychiatric and medical comorbidities in depression management through multidisciplinary approaches is essential for comprehensive patient care. By embracing these future prospects and recommendations, clinicians and researchers can strive towards enhancing the quality of care and outcomes for individuals living with unipolar depression.

Conclusion

The study highlights the significant burden of depressive symptoms experienced by individuals with unipolar depression and underscores the intricate relationship between cognitive impairments and depressive symptomatology. Tailored interventions addressing both cognitive functioning and depressive symptoms are crucial for optimizing outcomes and improving the well-being of patients. Early detection, comprehensive assessment, and personalized management strategies are essential in psychiatric settings to enhance patient care

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